

WORLD PRACTICES ON URBAN LAND USE AND TERRITORY
PLANNING

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Abstract: In this thesis, urban use and spatial planning are considered an important role in the development of cities, determination of land use, creation of infrastructure and sustainable development. , aimed at meeting the needs of the population for housing, work, recreation and other social services

The main part. Urban use and spatial planning are important aspects of urban development and sustainable development. They include the processes of identifying, using and managing land resources in urban settings. Urban land use and spatial planning help to optimize land use, create comfortable and functional urban spaces, and solve problems related to population growth, infrastructure, and the environment. In this article, we consider the main principles, tools and problems of urban use and spatial planning, as well as examples of successful practices in this field.

The concept of urban land use

Urban land use is the process of planning, managing and using land resources in an urban setting. It involves the development and implementation of plans for the placement of various activities such as residential, commercial, industrial and public facilities on specific plots of land in the city.

Urban land use is aimed at effective use of land resources, improvement of the urban environment, creation of comfortable and functional urban spaces, as well as meeting the needs of the population for housing, work, recreation and other social services.

The main purposes of urban land use are:

- Development of master plans and city boundaries;
- determining the zoning of the territory for different types of land use;
- Determination of requirements for development and beautification of urban areas;
- Monitor compliance with established rules and regulations;
- development and implementation of urban infrastructure development projects;
- Land formation and regulation of land relations.

The use of urban land is an important means of creating stable and developed cities that provide comfortable living and working conditions for the population, as well as contribute to the economic and social development of the entire region.

Examples of successful practices in urban use and spatial planning

Copenhagen, Denmark

Copenhagen is known for its innovative approaches to urban use and spatial planning. One of the most successful examples is the Nyhavn district, which was transformed from a port area into a residential and commercial area. The creation of large squares, recreational parks, bicycle paths and pedestrian zones has become attractive for local residents and tourists.

Singapore

Singapore is an example of successful urban planning and land use. The city-state actively uses the use of vertical land, builds high-rise buildings and creates multi-level gardens and parks on the roofs of buildings. It saves space and creates green areas in the city.

Curitiba, Brazil

Curitiba is known for its innovative approaches to urban use and spatial planning. Public transport is actively developing in the city, a system of fast bus lines and bicycle paths is being created. Curitiba is also known for its parks and green areas that create a pleasant environment for residents.

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Table on "Urban Use and Territorial Planning".

Topic Description Features

From urban areas use The process of managing and using land resources in urban conditions -Determining the goals and objectives of land use

- Developing plans and projects for the development of urban areas
- Regulate land use according to established rules and regulations
- Optimizing the use of land resources to ensure sustainable development of the city

Territorial planning The process of developing and implementing plans for the development and use of urban areas - Determination of the functional purpose of land plots

- Determining the parameters of development and beautification of the area
- Considering environmental, social and economic factors in planning
- Ensuring the comfort and safety of citizens

Principles of urban land use and regional planning Basic principles guiding the development and implementation of urban land use and regional planning plans

- Sustainable development
 - Social justice
 - Economic efficiency
 - Environmental sustainability
- The integrity of the city

Tools and methods of urban use and spatial planning Tools and approaches used for the development and implementation of urban use and spatial planning plans -Legislation and regulatory documents

- Master plans and boundary plans
- Urban planning regulations and building regulations
- Analysis and forecasting of city development
- Public participation and stakeholder consultation

Urban Land Use and Spatial Planning Issues and Challenges Current Issues and Problems Cities Face in Developing and Implementing Urban Land Use and Spatial Planning Plans -Land Resources Lack

- Obsolete infrastructure
- Environmental problems
- Social inequalities
- Inefficient use of land

Examples of successful practices in urban use and spatial planning Notable examples of cities that have successfully implemented urban use and spatial planning - Copenhagen, Denmark

- Curitiba, Brazil

- Singapore
- Curitiba, Brazil
- Vancouver, Canada

Summary

Urban use and spatial planning play an important role in urban development and sustainable development. They make it possible to optimize the use of land resources, create comfortable and functional urban areas, as well as solve environmental and social infrastructure problems. The principles of urban use and spatial planning, as well as the tools and methods used in this field, help to create a sustainable and harmonious urban environment. At the same time, there are also problems and challenges related to the use of cities, such as land scarcity, urbanization and climate change. It is important to develop and implement successful urban use and planning practices to create resilient and sustainable cities for future generations.

List of used literature

1. Resolution No. 1023 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of December 20, 2019 "On measures to further improve the procedure for granting vacant land plots for the implementation of entrepreneurship and urban planning activities."
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3. Ashurov. A.F. "State urban planning cadastre" 2017
4. Internet Information.